

Transcription of Roundtable Caribbean Virtual Museums: Opportunities and Challenges

Museums Association of the Caribbean Conference 2018

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Panelists: Natalie McGuire-Batson – Barbados Museum & Historical Society, Karin Weil – Universidad Austral de Chile, Suzanne Francis-Brown – University of the West Indies, Dr Adeola Fabola – University of St Andrews, Dr Sherene James Williamson – University of the West Indies, Dr Alan Miller – University of St Andrews

Attendees mentioned: Anne Bancroft – V&A Museum, Catherine Anne Cassidy – University of St Andrews

Transcription

Alan: So thank you everybody for coming. This is a roundtable discussion on “The Caribbean Virtual Museums: Opportunities and Challenges”. We were discussing what was going to happen here, and it’s a little magical mystery tour, so we’ll find out at the end of it, rather than the beginning of it. By the idea is to have a conversation with our esteemed panel, our esteemed audiences, around those issues. I think we can start with like, so what do you we mean by virtual museum sand what so rt of things do we do we envisage they could be, and what are the challenges, and what are the opportunities and see where it goes from there.

(panel introductions)

Alan: Thinking forward in five or ten years’ time, notion of virtual museums what do you think it will be like, what do you want it to be like?

Karin: I’m not a technological person, in our own reality the museums in the places where we work, virtual museums is not something yet that’s happening because of connection, because of internet. In five or ten years thinking forward, it will probably be more real. But also, important to get little and big histories seen by people, so these are very important for doing this. But also, very important not lose the value or core of the community museums, being there and having the experience, hearing the history, smelling...its another experience to see without being there, without the humidity, cold, smell how they are cooking bread to share with you because they want to share their histories. So you have to go in somehow in a balanced way in which you can use this tool to make a lot of sense and make it better but not to forget what is the real sense of the museum, thinking not at university, not as a professional, but in their reality of the small or medium museums.

Suzanne: One of the concerns raised in relation to the virtual museum situation, at the community museum we spent the day at in Portland, what was effect of the exposure of their very valued artefacts have on visitor potential. I know its something for many people in the museum community it’s a don’t worry about it as long as it brings more people, but there is a concern for people in smaller museums especially in communities about impact would it have on visitor potential is an important thing for them. And that whole communication and educational aspect has to be addressed especially if your working with community and community museums.

Karin: Yes, you are bringing more people but more people does it make sense of that museum, wasn’t created it to bring more people. It was created for identity, memory, human rights, native

population or whatever in Latin American and Caribbean. So, I think it important to attract more people and make it more known but also you have to have a balance.

Natalie: I agree with both of those sentiments, I think there definitely needs to be space to carve out the community ethos and aspect and that doesn't get lost within the virtual sphere. I also think, that that's looking at their collections going out, but the virtual museum is a way to build agency within those museums in terms of what they can share with their own networks and their own publics that come, so getting back to Alan's question about the five year vision, one of the things we do, and I think a lot of Caribbean museums do, take some of our temporary exhibitions and have travel around to local libraries to spaces where they may not be going to the Barbados museum but we can go to them and I see the virtual museum maybe in the future be one way to further that reach so that these libraries, these community centres instead of to rely on us to bring panels to them they could download interpretative material provided by institutions and share reach and build agency within their own spaces without having to rely so much on larger institutions in the future.

Suzanne: I think resourcing is definitely a factor there though, I don't think it's a one size fits all situation, in other words I think there are certain situations would work better with a virtual capacity, but there are others where the balance has to be quite different, perhaps its more of a support for a continued physical engagement.

Adeola: I agree with what you guys have said, but there's one thing I'd like to add, and it's that what we say when we say virtual museum what comes to mind most of the time is using some sort of technology of digital infrastructure to expediate or communicate heritage, and I think maybe we need to rethink how to frame that to museum practitioners because that's where the concerns stem from. When people hear of technology adoption, the concern becomes, well is this technology meant to replace our current way that we are currently doing things? Its possible that's the message that we've been getting across up to this point, but this message needs to change. Instead of saying, right here's some shiny technology to replace so and so, maybe we need to say here is some technology that could supplement how we do things, this technology could walk hand in hand with your existing processes and your existing infrastructure. And to come back to the point that you raised Suzanne about resourcing, I absolutely agree, what I'd say is we can consider the notion of a resource spectrum if you will, where as we know there are hundreds of thousands of museums across the world with varying resource availability. You have the big national museum with lots of backing and community museums with little to no infrastructure. I think it's possible to have some sort of framework where you can use some subtle technology with varying levels of cost and availability irrespective of the resources at the museum's disposal. For example, if you have a museum that has a blank check or unlimited resources then maybe you can go all out there, you can deploy the virtual reality exhibits, you could have dedicated digital exhibit and spaces. But for the little museum, or the community museums that maybe just has a hut or four walls and no electricity, take advantage of the digital literacies of the museum's visitors. What you'd find tourist people who visit these museums, walk into the museum with lots of computing power. They have mobile phones and they have tablets right and the computing power...

Adeola cont.: the computing power available in the average smart phone to is more than what powered our first trip to the moon in the 60s. This is something we can take advantage of at little to no extra cost to the museum. So yes, I agree there are resource constraints but we can think about how we can support museums at varying level of resource availability.

Suzanne: I think the issue of knowledge is one thing, I think the issue of support is another thing, and how sometimes how to access that. The whole business of vocabulary as you mentioned is really

important. I know my own lacks in this regard, I have been using “online” rather than “virtual”, as in my own head, a virtual space is totally three dimensional and completely built out, you know you’re in a room, it’s not just an object. That’s how I see virtual, I’m probably completely wrong. You know the whole thing with language and making sure everybody is talking about the same thing is also really important, but your right if there’s more material availability so that in a relatively simple fashion for nontechnical, but visionary people, there is material that can be accessed. And one of these things that I found interesting in the workshops was this notion that you can use simply a carousel and a camera and some software and created three dimensional objects and that one of things that really stood out for a lot of people who were involved in the EU-LAC workshops last year. It doesn’t have to be that you have to have 360 cameras and all of this, there are some simple techniques that get you on the bandwagon, so to speak.

Adeola: Absolutely I think one misconception is most people think of as if the barriers of entry are really really high, but rather the message we should be getting across is no, the barriers are entry are much lower now than they used to be, so with commodity technology, with smartphones that people have, with digital cameras that people walk about with, with lazy Susan’s in people kitchens...

Sherene: I’m Sherene James Williamson, I’m lecturer and museum curator in the department of geography and geology at UWI, and also immediate past president of MAC. So I run a geology museum, and it’s a little difficult because well trying to navigate the space in a natural history museum is a little different from maybe art and other exciting things because most people are “a rock is a rock is a rock”. But within the context of a virtual museum, my museum would benefit a lot, some of our collections people want to study them but Jamaica is quite far away from where the people are. So I’m seeing, in terms of a virtual space, making my collections accessible, whether by database initially, objects will take a little bit longer because when you’re studying fossils, there are a bit more intricacies to get things going, but to provide an online kind of a catalogue. But I also see my visitors participating more in making my virtual museum a virtual museum. In the way you can crowd source, I think if we enabled visitors to take their images, in whichever angle and aspect they take it, and they have their own narrative, once this goes up with a space with interpretation, if you remember the activity yesterday in the interpretation workshop, everyone had something different to say about the objects in the pictures. And I think when your visitors come, they also come with information, and if its something that they posted something that’s a misconception, it’s something that’s out there, and it gives you an opportunity to address that. So I see our online museum environment more interactive and more informative in the next couple years. People are now from other places being able to even post a similar picture from a different museum of something similar or something they think is this thing but its isn’t anymore. The way things change over time we can capture that very quickly in the virtual environment, and I believe that the way social media technology’s going, I think eventually people are going to latch on to educating themselves a little bit better using this, rather than just the fly by night things that we do. But I believe museum can become more impactful for people to plug in to be able to see what’s there even though its far away.

Suzanne: I have a dream moment four years ago Sherene, at the MAC 2014 conference, was an online museum of the Caribbean through using, as I said, my fight with virtual and online, but something that pulls together, pulls virtually without taking anybody’s collection items, and with full respect and referral back to them with queries, but to make the Caribbean accessible through an online space because the sea that separates us, the sea can join us, but for the most part but when it comes to people looking for information, it can separate us rather than join us. So I think that digital space can provide a different way of linking and providing information on the region, correct

information on the region. And I'm starting with the Caribbean but obviously it doesn't only have to be just that, for people in the Caribbean and not in the Caribbean.

Sherene: What we conceptualize, something similar for mac some years ago and then this virtual museum project came on and we thought it so exciting to join onto this, one of the things we had perceived, the same way as someone would go to TripAdvisor to find out about a destination, we want that for Caribbean museums. So the way you search for the best sea and sand and fun, you would be searching for culture, cultural type of activities, museums. Within that context, you would be plugging in in a similar way as Suzanne has indicated. So you'd be able to see a snapshot at what is happening inside different museums, but not only from some kind of central page, you link back to page of that museum so now you are in direct contact with that place and possibly that person. So you'd be able to visit a museum in the same way you want to go to a beach to a concert hall within the Caribbean. And I think that is a vision that we can actually have and for the kinds of discussions we've been having, I don't think we're very far away from it.

Suzanne: Yeah I think there are also things that can plug into it, so if somebody's talking about the indigenous story of the Caribbean, LAC has been talking about migration, there is other topic areas that I think the intention I think is to explore virtually. So think there is bits of it, but for me, you are offering people access to a Caribbean museum that is online, then you are connecting back to Caribbean museum that are online.

Natalie: With the virtual database there are two digital amps that's exist, one developed by Fresh Milk Art platform that has art spaces in the Caribbean, and it's a map and you click on it and you get directed, you can read more about the art space and get in contact. And there Csilla [Ariese-Vandemeulebroucke] from UMAC, she has one for community museums throughout. But yea if we can bridge all of them into this big centralized and have that depth of being able to see a bit more than just what the...

Suzanne: It's kind of like UWI right? You have the regional story and you have the campus story. Its kind of like that, that's how I see it.

Anne: One of the earlier questions as well as the reason, with increasing accessibility to their collections and to the region, and sharing, and the whole virtual imaging and virtual reality is very fantastic and the five year question of going forward what will this look like. So increase of visibility and increase of collections people increasing visitors, and how will museums cope with this. There was a thing about a touring exhibition, and actually touring physical objects, and I'm not too sure why it just seems really expensive to not be able to tour the actual artefacts, and the infrastructure there to support that, but with the virtual I do suspect, people normally, in my experience, you put something online, then they'll go ok great, I want to borrow this. There's been a catalogue in this particular exhibition, both regionally as well as internationally, how would museums and the collections that you're in charge of, what is the infrastructure in order to support that is by ship by sea, how are you commission reporting process involved and how do you meet the criteria.....maybe that's too many questions.

Sherene: I think it's a work in process.

Suzanne: I think virtual overcomes some of that though.

Anne: It does, but the interest and the draw to the original object, the virtual is like a seed or a hook and then you want to see the original object, and the people want, this is thing the Erroll Barrow Hugh wore, this is original document. There is a kind of, at the risk of sounding like a hippie, a

resonance, an energy to that, and this is the strength of the collection. Yes the collection needs to be accessible, and I suspect and I hope it would protect ... to move the collections and what we ... Original object and openly admit eventually to have proper scientific analysis in the... at least being done on these incredible objects.

Sherene: I think the barrier to that is the insurance for the people who want to showcase it. At least in the short term I think the exhibition will go to specific cases and that will be paid for, probably, out of EU-LAC. But in terms of a physical item, they could probably be do 3d printing so we can replicate several of them but in terms of fabric type things so I think this is ... you'd like to, but we necessarily need to incorporate into the process. Some things that will not travel, for sure. You have paintings that probably will be part of the collections that no one will afford the insurance and all that is required to move the item, but certainly prints could move. A properly framed prints could move. But I think coupled with that, I think a virtual environment needs to follow it. And the suggestion of the borrowing and the booking of the exhibition and doing all of that online as if you were in a museum, walking into the museum with all of your paperwork but doing it in an online environment is really really exciting. I think one of the things we need to do, take something from the young people. This Pokémon Go, we could do this with artefacts! I don't know maybe it's weird, but you could do one that is Caribbean wide for the traveller, someone who will move from island to island. Especially for people who have to pass through an airport, because sometimes traveling through the Caribbean you have to go through two or three airports to get where you're going....and then of course you can have those that are local. And all of this can be set up using the same virtual environment if you a virtual museum of the Caribbean, because then you already have the images and so you'd be using your you know, so if you're in Jamaica Pokémon Go, or MuseumMan Go or something. And I think with all that is currently available in the sphere of virtual reality and augmented reality, as our museums are evolving, bring our museums into to the 22nd century, because it think it will be, I don't want to use the cliché cutting edge, but I think the youngsters who have not yet latched onto what learning takes on in a museum environment. I mean their walking into cars because of Pokémon Go, and I think I want them to walk into a museum instead.

Natalie: I wanted to add on about the challenges of shipping items physically as well in Ann's questions and some of it, unfortunately at least for Barbados, has to do with furthering our cultural policy around transporting artefacts as well. So having separate, I guess, regulations within customs for art and artefacts as opposed to commercial shipping. And right now, its quite a difficult area...

Sherene: Because handling is very important.

Natalie: ... and that all adds to the cost, if there's no distinction, even if you say its for educational purposes, that can only get you so far. We all know inter-regional travel whether you're individually getting on a plane or getting something between the islands is one of the remnants of colonialism, restricting our access to each other. I believe Amanda Coulson from the national art gallery in the Bahamas have been making some strides within the Bahamian government with regards to these issues. Id have to check exactly what but having more conversations with out ministries of culture around specific policies and regulations for transporting...

Sherene: Its easier the item is small, if the item is large and it can't fit it in the overhead bin or under the seat, it's not a problem because you're not going to put it in the hold.

Natalie: Or a whole exhibition.

Alan: I'd like to pick on Adeola, because he has a whole feast of opportunities and things to do with virtual museum has been raised, but Ade, you've spent a certain amount of time looking at

technologies and communities and virtual museums. So can I ask you, do you think this stuff is possibility, and if so, how? And then if we have a how, then a when.

Adeola: Do I think its possible, yes absolutely. How would it work? Well, I think a couple things come to mind, and to one of the ideas you proposed earlier. I think crowdsourcing can be really central, the successful implementation and operation of this idea. The notion that you're opening up the conversation up to everyone and anyone who is willing to contribute to it. So with the idea of touring exhibitions, for example, you get lots of people traveling across islands and if someone spots a painting somewhere in a museum, they could take a photo, they could tag it with their geolocation to say hey I found this Barbados Museum & Historical Society and what do you guys think of this, for example. This would go into the ether somewhere and it would be available for anyone else who is interested in searching for that painting for example. Someone could do a search for the painting and find that, say two days, ago, someone tagged it in Barbados museum, so that way you can kind of see, you could track the path that painting will travel across the Caribbean. That's one an example of how that would work. We could add augmented reality on top of that, where you take your phone into the museum, hold it up against the artefact or painting, and right there get a lot of information, annotations on top of that. You can choose to add to it, so if you have a personal story, or something that's been in your family for generations you can add to that discussion as well. I think one potential challenge associated when you open things up to the public, you may get unforeseen responses, trolls essentially. But we can control that, you can have moderators what's been contributed and approving and deleting comments as required. Again, I don't know if I've said anything about geolocation, but I think it's important for such a system or infrastructure is location aware. So if that means taking advantage of GPS in people's phones, or installing beacons in museums across the Caribbean, things that would associate artefacts with places temporarily. I think that could work nicely. There's so many opportunities here, so many possibilities that our technology would allow, no doubt there would be challenges, but if the interest is there, the tech circles and the heritage experts could work together for a viable solution.

Sherene: And of course, the guys that like to study focus groups would be able access impact. So that's something you can actually; you have all these comments and all these likes and all this information, this can distil into impact. So you know if this was impactful or not, you know.

Suzanne: I think one of the things also there's lots of different layers that are possible, and but seems to me that you talk about any kind of museum situation of that sort, you talk about a full tank thing, you're not talking about an add on to somebody's existing job description. Because that tends to be part of the process.

Sherene: it would require a curator.

Suzanne: Yeah, in getting something ahead. But I think you can have the layers that are to do with in a sense social media at it is now, where you can have communication you can have inputting material as well as taking back. One of the things we do at UWI museum is to build the oral history as a counter point to the administrative and official histories. And I'm sure that is something that can be done via some sort of online platform. It seems to me some of things Sherene has in mind, some of the things I have in mind. But he asked about dreams and visions, we haven't gotten to the point how the heck do you make it work, because I've been talking about this for four years and I haven't got too far.

Anne: that's where you got to start is with dream and visions.

Suzanne: The other thing when I was talking about some of the things in a sense, input into the same overlap, Alex was talking yesterday, he had in mind a museum actually moving around the Caribbean like on a boat, sort of like the old (federal Palmen maple?), which is the first thing I thought of, but I think he wants his boat to be an instrument I think. But the point is, that is one methodology, but virtual is another methodology, and the two things, you could have geotags on the boat, you could go to one menu item and track the boat and see where its going next.

Sherene: much like rose hope?

Suzanne: Something like that, and the tourism association was interested in what he was talking about.

Anne: It might be a bit short of mundane, but language? All the different languages as well. I assume this is something that could be quite easy to be able to interpret the object, use google translate or how easy is the, in the database or the technology for this?

Adeola: Well, Google translate is an option, but it's not always reliable.

Sherene: Narrative is complicated to understand.

Anne: So how do you normally deal with the different languages in the region or something like that in the realm of technology.

Adeola: Good question, I'm not entirely sure. So why I imagine this working, Suzanne said something about this potential solution not being you slap onto something, but it would be its own thing. So I think that could open up job opportunities, it could open new positions for digital curators in this space. I could imagine a job title that would be something like digital translator or something with those words in it, but people who would specialize facilitating this cross language and communications and conversations. To go back to your question about the impact this could have, I think that if the learnings the recent exhibition we did in Scotland is anything to go by we can say that there is quite a public appetite for this kind of thing. To be more specific, last year our team ran a three-month exhibition in Scotland, we called the Picts & Pixels exhibitions. It was focusing on the Picts that lived in the Perth area of Scotland.

Alan: How many years ago?

Adeola: So we have a historian on our team.

Alan: About 600 years.

Adeola: I was just testing you.

Natalie: I actually have a question that stems for my fellow panellists if that's ok and anyone as well, and its been something we've been thinking about as well, and that is how do you feel using virtual technologies and virtual museums helps or hinders our publics that come in with different physical and learning abilities. Is it something that can enhance those experiences or how would we navigate having maybe a child with autism coming in, is it too much stimulation? In that sense, just your thoughts?

Alan: *says something about time*

Sherene: I want to say one name, Catherine Cole. She had some activities in the last year where they were looking at access, and it would be disability access etc. But it wasn't in terms of physical access,

but how people interact with collections when they have a various kinds of impairment. So if you talk to Catherine, she might have something to suggest about that.

Suzanne: I think there is possibilities. I don't think there's a one size fits all.

Sherene: There's lots of technology out there....

Alan: I have to say, a lot of the time, people get on through life with a very limited set of literacies and that some people actually respond quite well to virtual environments because they find them less threatening, less conventual, more at ease in them. We had done some work in Scotland working with schools of people with different ways of learning; its often been quite a leveller. So the people who are frightened doing maths or pen and the pencil feel more confident in a digital environment and consequently get on much better, but I'm that needs to sorted about. We're kind of running out time.

Catherine: Because we touched on it when we started, and we just brought it back up and I want to just ask to people who are in museums about workflows and about who would then these responsibilities either creating digital content or at least curating and managing and working with a virtual museum, who right now or who you see who would take that on, in your museum structure where that would go to, and what would be those workflows, or you can see envisioning or what is already going in your museum, to take on this digital work.

Sherene: the way I envision it, and probably white horses and unicorns, I think well have to start with a model of soliciting images from different museums across the region. This has to go to a central place where somebody will have to put this together. But we will need three or four (Sets) because you need that many languages with the same objects, in simple terms. You also need sort of a discovery area where the autistic child could do a jigsaw puzzle pottery. But the fact is, that well have to start with soliciting collections in the same way you would if you were developing a new museum, you would start to solicit pieces from different places. And once you get it in some repository, you now have to create your story. It could be thematic, it could chronological... manage to collect, and then somebody would now have to curate all of these items. Within the context of individual museums, whoever your museums curator, or manager, you can make somebody responsible sending these objects, and you can decide within your own institution what objects would be of note to join into this particular collection. where it goes from there is a matter of the dynamics of this curator and digital team.

Someone from the crowd: I guess we have an example at the University of Florida, that has put together the archives of the Caribbean, the digital library of the Caribbean, so I guess that's a ... to look at which I think it's a pretty small staff, three people or something like that.

Sherene: and all they do is solicit material, and their database is just so robust.

Suzanne: I see what you're asking in a slightly different way. I think as it stands, certainly at the University at the West Indies and many museums, small museums, the staff is a person, possibly two people and what I'm certainly dreaming about would require its own staff. I think it would require its own curator, possibly someone more directorial level to deal with some of the structuring in terms of pulling resourcing and personnel, contractual materials together, and it would require a technical component which we presently do not have. I think that the university is interested in looking at some possibilities within itself, but I don't think that structure currently exists, and mapping that structure is one of those steps that would have to be taken. But I don't think its an impossibility. The university was set up in 1948 and one of its mandates from the very beginning was contributing to

the regional story, was contributing to regional development and telling the Caribbean. So I think with the remnants of that in mind, this is not an impossible ask, but developing it and explaining to the people who make the decisions how this could be done, what the potential layers could be, what the benefits could be, in very current terms. I think all of that would have to be put in place. But I feel that it would have to be, it could not be curating my physical space at the UWI museum as these guys know has a staff of one. Presently and a half, I'm really working on that half. You can't do this as a whole; it requires partnerships, it requires possibilities, and I said some of the elements that already there and pull them together and create would be a useful approach but I do think it would have to stand alone, when I say standalone, I don't mean standalone. It will always come back to the museums that exists, come back to other things. But standalone in terms of who's responsibility and who's outcomes. That's what I would see. It would have to have that.

Alan: *mentions about how with a staff of one, it seems like an army, wonder where she hides them all*

Suzanne: I think part of it is seeing the possibilities. I used to do some script writing, so see three dimensionally, I see the possibilities. To me then, how you translate those possibilities into a new reality, that is the challenge and that would be where it would be great to get people on board. Because you have to convince the persona who play the salaries there is something pragmatic and practical, that they can see in branding and in terms of And in the terms of academics and in research and all of that, that they can see where it all fits in.

Alan: I think its kind of like a lots of things they happen from the top down and the bottom up. And I think there's a lot of things that are happening in the digital world in any case. A lot of people are doing a bit of photogrammetry, a lot of people have drones, websites or fb pages a lot of museums have got those. I think that, the space we've been working in has been developing a bit of an infrastructure and some of that is there and Ade is going to be talking more about it in the next session.

Suzanne: Which I have to not be there.

Alan: ... but which takes that stuff that is emerging and tries to encourage to build.

Suzanne: synthesize it.

Alan: ...and synthesize it and build up on it. And I suspect when that gets to a certain level, then the people who sit and work out how many of us are going to be and what our salaries are going to be, pennies might start dropping.

Suzanne: but can I just say something, but you know... you when you feel when you have an idea that's really quite bright? But you had it early? But the times everybody catches up, it's just pedestrian.

Alan: its like Leonardo and the helicopter.

Karin: I just wanted to add, hearing and I agree mostly. I think that first of all, we have to think about, so far I hear, virtual museum and technology can have a lot of useful parts, but answering your question, and staff and requirement in payment, you must first know who is engaged, for what. I want to use the virtual museum for getting more people, to get in TripAdvisor. The person that has to be in charge of that is the one who is doing tourism or relationship or whatever. If you want to go and make a digital or virtual museum with the whole collection, its probably the curator or the people who work at the collections department, or conservators. Because if you don't have clear

even for social inclusion, if you use your virtual museum for that kind of programme, you're knowing with whom to work with. And you know what for, then you can evaluate it and then prove that its useful because you got what you were looking for. I think that's very important from the beginning, if you say we want to start the virtual museum to put this museum in the (mirror?). and we took it because we can show how many people who visit them through the internet, or if the people who coming increase, now you can go to the authorities and say look, these tools help. But we have to know for what. And I think that's one of the first questions. Who is going to be in charge of the virtual museum, for what, and maybe increasing, you can use it for a lot of things. But each one has to be directly in touch with that.

Alan: I think we've run out of time, so what I wanted to do was to see if anybody had any questions.

Someone in the crowd: just to go back to someone comments, about creating content with limited employees, but the biggest thing isn't about creating content, its being able to store and preserve it long term. Who would have the responsibility? It comes down to infrastructure because you need serve, you need engineers, you need computer science people to keep the stuff forever. Otherwise you can upload pictures and then next year you may not find them.

Sherene: Sustainability.

Alan: Do if I just take from the audience any other questions that there are, and then ill ask our esteemed panel to come back no the questions for the final time.

Anne: How do we generate income from the virtual museum?

Someone in the crowd: I think it's a really interesting question this idea of why are you building and who are you building it for. What are their needs are whether its language or audio description, or what kind of experience they might need. But it seems to me that this element of crowdsourcing, and how it can be issues based, so maybe every year there's a different story being told with the objects that are there to keep it alive and keep it fresh. That's something I would aspire to in a virtual exhibition in the future there's something about it that lives and breathe just like the museums we walk into the live and breathe and I think that's really hard because often in a virtual environment, get it digitized, make it available, and check. And how to make sure it doesn't just fall into that.

Alan: fantastic, if we go right to left and go across, final opportunity to answer question, and say anything you want in closing. Don't feel obliged to answer each the questions, as long as somebody does.

Natalie: I guess in relation to Ann's question, at the moment we've only been thinking about bite sized ways to generate income, not massive ways through the curatorial department. And that would be membership, curatorial services and training. I can expand a little bit. The membership is if we have a virtual museum space attached to our museum website in the future, that could be a membership perks. So having restricted access to our digitalized collections could be one of the membership tear perk, and maybe that could bring income. And curatorial services, what I've been doing is if a company want us to do a presentation, or an artefact display, and around independence we od get a lot of requests. They have a lot of independence, Barbados independence day is at the end of this month, and a lot companies have staff event celebrating our day of independence and ask our museum to come and do historical presentations with artefacts, so what I've been doing is trying to enhance that process by offering a walkthrough of what we digitize in our collections as well as part of that presentations, so that could be another bite sized in generating income. Training

although we try to offer, the summer intensive we had this year was free, and we you know much to our finance officers dismay, but that could be, if professionals from maybe the islands who didn't participate in the EU-LAC project if they wanted to come to a space and a training session based on what we learned by sharing with them, that could maybe be monetized in some way. But those are very large income generating, but trying to incorporating into bite sized...

Suzanne: I think one of the benefits of a Caribbean virtual museums space, if looking at from UWI one of the things that the university if focusing on is pan-UWI complete Caribbean perspective which is one of the things is was set up to do. And I think from that perspective of knowledge creation and knowledge sharing, it would be something useful and possible, and perhaps pull in many elements of the university's teaching and learning endeavour, as well the level of students as lecturers. I kind of see from that perspective. Don't know the answer in terms of how to at the moment, how to pay all the bills. I agree Natalie that it terms of membership services, maybe access to certain levels of collections and sort of thing and things can be done where that is concerned. But I think that there are benefits that are broader that have to do with just sharing of knowledge. I think that the point that you raised Ann and you (Karin) raised in terms of having a strong sense on why you are doing what you are doing, and therefore making sure....or instance you were talking about community museums and if that's what that it is, its not the same if you are just trying to reach a wider audience, perhaps provide knowledge, make a connection for your own business and for the university its certainly knowledge. I think there are a lot more questions than answers, but I think it could be an exciting kind of project, and that's one of the things that attracts me to it. I think there a lot of new ways of sharing knowledge, communicating, doing the research, getting it out there. There's a lot of short comings, like server space. Just for social media and taking pictures, and saving videos and pictures is a huge, already a challenge. And so that has to be something to be taken into account.

Karin: but you answered for me. I was saying somehow the same thing. But I just want, and really I was thinking about this also, but instead of answering I maybe share with you that the question of how to get it sustainability during time because you have now the know-how, we have more the parts, the EU-LAC workshops but after, what's happening after. If I got out of museums, not working anymore there, who's going to continue, who's going to get training from whom. And I think it's something that's interesting, it's a really nice challenge, and I can see how it can go and increase a lot of mostly sharing, sharing knowledge. From university to traditional knowledge. I think it happens somehow. But how to do get into the future, because new generation knows very well how to use technology but museums for sharing, starting with what you were saying, were thinking about heritage, memory, history, values, different kind of values, symbolic or personal or whatever. But how can we continue doing that without the people who know how to use the technology, the tools. I did not get to answer but to think.

Adeola: To answer your question Ann, how to make money out of things like this. I imagine two things, one that we can copy of what a lot of apps do, which is adopt a kind Freemian model, you can get the service for free, and when you get hooked on the content for bits then there's things you have to pay for.

Sherene: in app purchases

Adeola: In app purchases for example. Another thing you can do on top of that is adopt gamification. Where thinking back to apps like Pokémon go, if there's a task or goal or a task you have to do to obtain a certain goal, and if they're really invested in it, you can do things like offer packs for them to buy to accomplish those goals quicker. So gamification tends to provide strong motivation for people

to do things and if people are willing to pay for the gamified aspects for your service, there's an opportunity to make a lot of money out of it and still get our heritage out into the world in the process. And the other questions about how to insure continuity and some kind of sustainability mode. Yes, it's a difficult one, it's a challenge and the way we've approached the problem is we don't think of ourselves as the tech guys or the scientists and therefore everyone has to depend on us, but how can we empower people with the skill set and the technical know how to do these things themselves. Yes, it would require some infrastructure and we tend to provide that. We have servers and back ups backed up by a reputable university to hopefully those things won't go away anytime soon. But if we have some sort of content management interface in front of that and then encourage people to supply the content the digitized and it gets stored in the back end, there's a good chance that that could live on, that could provide a curation management services and that could help in terms of preserving that digital heritage. We still need to address the issues of raising awareness, insuring that those skills are passed on within the museum or within your community, but that's something that we all need to work together towards. There's no short cuts in my mind.

Sherene: the difficulty with going last is that everyone has said what you were thinking. A couple of years ago we had a MAC conference in the caiman islands, and our colleagues from NAAMHC and they described in a presentation about starting this new museum, and the model that they have is a model we could, I don't want to say adopt but maybe adapt. Being there I can see a lot of the media and a lot of the content and storage heavy material that is there and in terms of the technical capabilities that's one thing we could get advice on but in the terms of the structure of the obtaining the collections and how to compartmentalise them and how to set them in stories and how things work from the point of view from staff and the arrangement of staff and how things come all the way down to the collections. I think if we were to exercise a model like that we would be able to find a structure within which this could work. Because this is fairly recent, it has a lot media and storage heavy material and I think it's probably something we can engage them to just see how their collections policy and their staffing and set up is to allow them some opportunity to work with this. But that's one thing I do in app purchases on I'm sitting here thinking about in app purchases. I don't play Pokémon Go but candy crush or museum crush or that some kind of game, jewel quest.

Alan: Thank you very much everybody, thank you so much for the panel. I learned so much and so many different questions and approaches and answers. I thought that was an incredibly rich discussion. I would really like to be involved in writing it up in some way, if we take that forward and if anyone is interested and from the audience that would be really great. Thank you so much for the panel and thank you so much for the questions.

Biographies of Roundtable Panellists

Natalie McGuire-Batson is a Barbadian curator and researcher whose work focuses on community-driven critical discourse in culture, through repositioning frameworks of research on Caribbean art, as well as digitally housed creative exchange projects. Currently a PhD candidate in Cultural Studies at the UWI Cave Hill, Natalie is also the Assistant Curator of Social History and Engagement at the Barbados Museum and Historical Society, and has coordinated exchange projects and exhibitions for platforms such as Fresh Milk, CARIFESTA, The Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa and Gallery NuEdge. In 2015 she was the art writer in residence for Caribbean Linked III, and has contributed articles for ARC Magazine, AICA SC, MOKO Magazine, Caribbean Beat, as well as artist exhibition catalogues.

Suzanne Francis-Brown is a writer, editor, historian and curator of the University of West Indies Museum located the university Mona location in Jamaica. She has been focusing on the history and heritage of the UWI and its Mona site since she did her MA Heritage Studies there in 1999. She went on to complete a PhD in history, titled: 'Gibraltar Camp 1940-1947. Isolation and Interaction in Colonial Jamaica'.

Karin Weil is an anthropologist and is the Director of the UACH Museological Direction and a professor at the Faculty of Art and Architecture in Pre-graduate and Post-graduate Studies as well as an expert advisor in the area of cultural heritage management. She was responsible for the formation of the Política Cultural de la Región de los Ríos 2016-2020.

Dr Adeola Fabola is a recent PhD from the School of Computer Science at the University of St Andrews. His research focused on using mobile, web, games, virtual reality and real-time communication technologies for community-centric virtual museums and immersive heritage exploration.

Dr Sherene James Williamson is Lecturer and Museum Curator at the Department of Geography and Geology at The University of the West Indies, Mona Campus. She is the previous president of the Museums Association of the Caribbean (MAC). She is the editor for the MAC flagship scholarly publication Caribbean Museums as well as editor for the Caribbean Journal of Earth Science (formerly, Journal of the Geological Society of Jamaica). Dr. James-Williamson's primary areas of research are sedimentary geology, geoheritage and geoarchaeology. Sherene holds a BSc in Earth Science (2001) and a PhD in Geology (2008) both from the University of the West Indies, Mona Campus.

Dr Alan Miller (moderator) is a lecturer in Cultural Heritage at the University of St Andrews. As part of the EU-LAC MUSEUMS project he worked with museums in the Caribbean, developing a Caribbean Virtual Museum in Migration and participating a series of workshops on 3D and Spherical Technologies with museums in Jamaica, Trinidad and Tobago and Barbados. Alan leads the Open Virtual Worlds team in the School of Computer Science at St Andrews which develops innovative technology for the preservation and promotion of heritage.